

Mathematical Analysis of the Co-Dynamics of Dengue–COVID–19 Coinfection

Jenije, Richard*

Department of Mathematics
Delta State College of Education,
Mosogar, Delta State

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-6633-1043>

Aghanenu, Odogwu Emeke

Department of Mathematics,
Delta State University,
Abraka, Delta State

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0027-7806>

Abstract

*This paper sought to analyze theoretically the co-dynamics of Dengue-COVID-19 coinfection with a mathematical model. The formulated model divides the human population into 12 compartment and the vector population (*aedes aegypti*) into 3 subpopulations. The qualitative examination of the Dengue and COVID-19 models shows that the DFE is locally asymptotically stable provided the corresponding reproduction numbers are less than unity. The COVID-19 sub-model is globally asymptotically stable as a Lyapunov function was constructed to show its stability. On analysis, the coinfection model exhibited the phenomenon of backward bifurcation at $R_{cd} = 1$ and it was shown that two parameters were responsible for the existence of backward bifurcation in the coinfection model (6) and they include; 1) the probability of effective transmission of dengue from infectious humans to susceptible *aedes aegypti* vectors (Φ_7) and (2) the susceptibility of COVID-19 infected individuals to dengue infection (Φ_6). It was also discovered that an increase in the spread of COVID-19 pandemic does not significantly affect the spread of dengue infection in the community and an increase in the spread of dengue infection in the community will increase the pandemic of COVID-19.*

Keywords: Dengue, COVID-19, Bifurcation, Coinfection, Transmission.

Introduction

The novel coronavirus (COVID-19) is a contagious virus that infects the respiratory system of humans and has caused millions of deaths worldwide. The spread of the virus to over 210 countries in 2020, resulted to a pandemic which up till now still generates severe public health concern worldwide. The virus when introduced to the human body, results in difficulty in breathing and as such might lead to severity in organ damage or cause the death of the individual carrying the virus. When an infected person coughs in public, healthy individuals around the infected are usually at risk of contracting the disease and as such there is need for isolation of infected individuals so as to avoid contact with healthy individuals.

As stated by Chowell et al. (2007), Dengue a common mosquito-borne viral infection is evident in many countries like Africa, America, the Eastern Mediterranean, South East Asia and the West Pacific. Dengue has been discovered in more than 100 countries and an estimated 2.5 billion people live in areas where dengue is endemic. Humans acquire dengue infection through the bites of *aedes aegypti* female mosquitoes known to be the chief vectors. Apart from *aedes aegypti*, some other species like *aedes albopictus* are also significant. Dengue causes severe flu-like illness and sometimes leads to a harmful complication called Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF). It has been reported by WHO (2012), that over 2.5% of individuals who acquire dengue infection die as a result of the infection since dengue has no vaccine yet. Dengue disease is caused by

*Corresponding Author: jenijerichard@gmail.com

four different serotype virus known as DEN 1, DEN 2, DEN 3 and DEN 4. It is important to note that both DEN 2 and DEN 3 are the most common serotypes in tropical countries. An individual who is infected by one of the four serotypes will be permanently immuned to that particular serotype but could get infected by the other three serotypes. This strain specific immune response according to WHO (2012), may also provide partial or temporal immunity against other serotypes and then revert back to becoming more susceptible especially to developing Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF). Dengue disease has now become a major global public health issue. The World Health Organization in 2012 reported that the disease burden of dengue has increased drastically. The cases of dengue disease increased from 1.2 million in 2008 to 2.2 million in 2010 across several continents such as America, South East Asia and West pacific. It was estimated that almost half the world population about 2.5 billion people are at risk of dengue. According to WHO (2016) estimation, there are over 50 million annual dengue cases annually all over the world and about 500,000 severe cases of dengue infection which requires hospitalization. A large proportion of these severe cases are children.

Dengue-COVID-19 coinfection is a situation where both Corona virus and dengue disease exist in a patient at the same time. both diseases may coexist due to geographical overlap as they are found in tropical and sub-tropical areas. Both diseases may share clinical and laboratory features making clinical diagnosis is difficult. The first case of co-infection of dengue fever and COVID-19 was reported by Verduyn et al. (2020) in a French overseas department located in the Indian Ocean. Similarly, Lansbury et al. (2020) gave a comprehensive review of the data on plausible co-infection in a single individual of dengue and COVID-19. Dengue-COVID-19 co-infection can create a high burden on communities and the health system in the affected areas as highlighted by Malibari et al (2020). It is pertinent to note according to Saddique et al. (2020), that the symptomatic appearance of COVID-19 and dengue infections are quite similar and may be hard to distinguish, although they are caused by different viruses. The similarity presented by both dengue and COVID-19 symptoms could lead to misdiagnosis of one disease for the other and therefore minimizing the extent of co-infection of the two diseases (Hussein et al., 2020).

Various mathematical models have been proposed to study infectious diseases. Arcede et al. (2020) proposed an extension from the traditional SEIR model by including an asymptomatic infected compartment. Similarly, Ahmed (2021) created a simple mathematical model with asymptomatic and symptomatic classifications to examine transmission and control of COVID-19. Biswas (2020) modeled the effect of self-immunity and the impacts of asymptomatic and symptomatic individuals on COVID-19. So many models have examined coinfection between COVID-19 and other infectious diseases. For example, TB and COVID-19 (Mekonen et al., 2022), COVID-19 and cholera (Hezam et al., 2021), dengue and leptospirosis (Alemneh, 2020), COVID-19 and diabetes (Ozkose and Yavuz, 2022), COVID-19 and HIV infection (Ringea et al., 2022), dengue and Zika (Bonyah et al., 2019). Several models have also been used to investigate COVID-19 and dengue co-interaction. One of the first such papers is the one by Omame et al (2021), in which they built and analyzed a mathematical model for the dynamics of COVID-19 and dengue transmission in Brazil, including optimal control and cost-effectiveness evaluations. The co-dynamics of dengue and COVID-19 coinfection in endemic vicinities might result in an epidemic outbreak. This can lead to a burden on a country’s healthcare infrastructure as well as finances. A mathematical model on the co-dynamics of dengue and COVID-19 coinfection is presented in response to the issues stated above.

Model Description

In this section, we develop a model for the co-dynamics of COVID-19 and dengue fever.

Model Formulation

The human population at time t , denoted by $N(t)$ is divided into the following epidemiological subgroups; wholly susceptible individuals (S_w), individuals exposed to dengue (E_d), individuals exposed to COVID-19 (E_c), individuals infected with dengue (I_d), individuals infected with COVID-19 (I_c), individuals who recover from dengue (R_d), individuals who recover from COVID-19 (R_c), quarantined individuals (Q), individuals exposed to both dengue and COVID-19 (E_{cd}), individuals infected with both dengue and COVID-19 (I_{cd}), dengue infected – COVID-19 exposed individuals (E_{cd}^c), dengue exposed – COVID-19 infected individuals (E_{cd}^d). Thus, the total human population is given by

$$N_h(t) = S_w + E_d + E_c + I_d + I_c + E_{cd} + E_{cd}^c + E_{cd}^d + I_{cd} + Q + R_d + R_c \tag{1}$$

The vector (*aedes aegypti*) population, denoted by $N_v(t)$ is divided into susceptible *aedes aegypti* (S_v), exposed *aedes aegypti* (E_v) and infectious *aedes aegypti* (I_v). Thus, we have

$$N_v(t) = S_v + E_v + I_v \tag{2}$$

Individuals acquire corona virus infection following contact with infected persons at a rate

$$\lambda_c = \frac{\beta_c(1-kp)[I_c + E_{cd}^d + I_{cd}]}{N_h - Q} \tag{3}$$

Where β_c is the probability for a human to be infected after effective contact with an infected person. The effect of personal protection is modeled by the factor $(1-kp)$, where $0 < k < 1$ is the efficacy of personal protection strategy adopted and $0 < p < 1$ is the fraction of the community employing (compliance) it, where $k = 1$ means 100% compliance and $k = 0$ means no compliance at all.

Individuals acquire dengue infection following effective contact with infected *aedes aegypti* (I_v) at a rate given by

$$\lambda_d = \frac{\beta_d b I_v}{N_h} \tag{4}$$

Where β_d is the transmission probability per bite and b is the per capita biting rate of *aedes aegypti*.

The population of susceptible *aedes aegypti* (S_v) acquire dengue infection following effective contact with humans at a rate

$$\lambda_v = \frac{\phi_7 \beta_v b [I_d + E_{cd}^c + I_{cd}]}{N_h} \tag{5}$$

Where β_v is the transmission probability of dengue infection, ϕ_7 is the

Let Λ_h be the recruitment rate of individuals into the wholly susceptible class (S_w). we assume that μ_h is the natural death rate in all epidemiological classes. Let δ_1 the dengue induced death rate for the infected class (I_d), δ_2 is the COVID-19 induced death rate for the infected class (I_c), δ_3 is the dengue induced death rate for the E_{cd}^c class and δ_4 is the COVID-19 induced death rate for the E_{cd}^d class. The parameter θ_d (θ_c) is the rate at which individuals migrate from dengue (COVID-19) exposed class to the dengue (COVID-19) infected class. The parameter r_d (r_c) accounts for recovery rates of the dengue (COVID-19) infected class. The parameters ϕ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) represents the modification parameters that accounts for infectiousness of individuals in the E_{cd} , E_{cd}^c , E_{cd}^d classes relative to those in the E_d and E_c classes. Individuals in the E_{cd} class move to the I_{cd} class at a rate θ_{cd} . In the same light, individuals in the E_{cd}^c (E_{cd}^d) class move to the I_{cd} class at a rate σ_c (σ_d). The individuals in the COVID-19 infected class are detected and quarantined at the rate φ . The quarantined individuals recover at the rate r_q and move to the R_c class.

Based on the assumptions above, our coinfection model for dengue and COVID-19 is given by the following system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations;

$$\frac{dS_w}{dt} = \Lambda_h + \varphi_1 I_{cd} - (\lambda_d + \lambda_c + \mu_h) S_w$$

$$\frac{dE_d}{dt} = \lambda_d S_w + \phi_4 \lambda_d R_c - (\phi_1 \lambda_c + \theta_d + \mu_h) E_d$$

$$\frac{dE_c}{dt} = \lambda_c S_w + \phi_3 \lambda_c R_d - (\phi_2 \lambda_d + \theta_c + \mu_h) E_c$$

$$\frac{dE_{cd}}{dt} = \phi_1 \lambda_c E_d + \phi_2 \lambda_d E_d - (\theta_{cd} + \mu_h) E_{cd}$$

$$\frac{dE_{cd}^c}{dt} = \phi_5 \lambda_c I_d - (\sigma_c + \mu_h + \delta_3) E_{cd}^c$$

$$\frac{dE_{cd}^d}{dt} = \phi_6 \lambda_d I_c - (\sigma_d + \mu_h + \delta_4) E_{cd}^d$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dI_d}{dt} &= \theta_d E_d - (\phi_5 \lambda_c + r_d + \mu_h + \delta_1) I_d \\
 \frac{dI_c}{dt} &= \theta_c E_c - (\phi_6 \lambda_d + \varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2) I_c \\
 \frac{dI_{cd}}{dt} &= \theta_{cd} E_{cd} + \sigma_c E_{cd}^c + \sigma_d E_{cd}^d - (\varphi_1 + \mu_h + \delta_1 + \delta_2) I_{cd} \\
 \frac{dQ}{dt} &= \varphi_2 I_c - (r_q + \mu_h) Q \\
 \frac{dR_d}{dt} &= r_d I_d - (\phi_3 \lambda_c + \mu_h) R_d \\
 \frac{dR_c}{dt} &= r_c I_c - (\phi_4 \lambda_d + \mu_h) R_c \\
 \frac{dS_v}{dt} &= \Lambda_v - (\lambda_v + \mu_v) S_v \\
 \frac{dE_v}{dt} &= \lambda_v S_v - (\theta_v + \mu_v) E_v \\
 \frac{dI_v}{dt} &= \theta_v E_v - \mu_v I_v
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

Table 1: Variables

Variables	Description
S_w	Wholly susceptible individuals
$E_d(E_c)$	Individuals exposed to dengue (COVID-19) disease
$I_d(I_c)$	Individuals infected with dengue (COVID-19) disease
$R_d(R_c)$	Individuals who are recovered from dengue (COVID-19) disease
Q	Individuals hospitalized due to detection of their COVID-19 status
$E_{cd}(I_{cd})$	Individuals exposed (infected) to both dengue and COVID-19 disease
E_{cd}^c	COVID-19 exposed – dengue infected individuals
E_{cd}^d	dengue exposed – COVID-19 infected individuals

2.2 Basic Properties of the Model

For the model (6) to be epidemiologically meaningful, we show that all its associated state variables are positive for all time, t .

Theorem 1: the model (6) preserves positivity of solutions.

Proof

Let $t_1 = \text{Sup} \{t > 0: S_w > 0, E_d > 0, E_c > 0, I_d > 0, I_c > 0, E_{cd} > 0, E_{cd}^c > 0, E_{cd}^d > 0, I_{cd} > 0, Q > 0, R_d > 0, R_c > 0, S_v > 0, E_v > 0, I_v > 0 \in [0, t]\}$

Thus $t_1 > 0$. It follows that from the first equation of model (6) that

$$\frac{dS_w}{dt} = \Lambda_h + \varphi_1 I_{cd} - (\lambda_d + \lambda_c + \mu_h) S_w \geq \Lambda_h - (\lambda_d + \lambda_c + \mu_h) S_w
 \tag{7}$$

Which can be written as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \{S_w(t) \exp[\mu_h t + \int_0^t (\lambda_d(\tau) + \lambda_c(\tau)) d\tau]\} \geq \Lambda_h \{ \exp[\mu_h t + \int_0^t (\lambda_d(\tau) + \lambda_c(\tau)) d\tau] \}. \text{ Thus}$$

$S_w(t_1) \exp[\mu_h t_1 + \int_0^{t_1} (\lambda_d(\tau) + \lambda_c(\tau)) d\tau] - S_w(0) \geq \int_0^{t_1} \Lambda_h \{ \exp[\mu_h y + \int_0^y (\lambda_d(\tau) + \lambda_c(\tau)) dy] \} dy$. So that,

$$S_w(t_1) = S_w(0)\exp[-\mu_h t - \int_0^{t_1} (\lambda_d(\tau) + \lambda_c(\tau))d\tau] + [\exp\{-\mu_h t - \int_0^{t_1} (\lambda_d(\tau) + \lambda_c(\tau)) d\tau\} \times \int_0^{t_1} \Lambda_h \{\exp[\mu_h y + \int_0^y (\lambda_d(\tau) + \lambda_c(\tau))dy]\} dy] > 0.$$

Similarly, it can be shown that $E_d > 0, E_c > 0, I_d > 0, I_c > 0, E_{cd} > 0, E_{cd}^c > 0, E_{cd}^d > 0, I_{cd} > 0, Q > 0, R_d > 0, R_c > 0, S_v > 0, E_v > 0, I_v > 0$ for all time $t > 0$. Hence, all solutions of model (16) remain positive for all non-negative initial conditions as required.

Theorem 2: The feasible region $\Omega_{cd} =$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (S, E_d, E_c, I_d, I_c, E_{cd}, E_{cd}^c, E_{cd}^d, I_{cd}, Q, R_d, R_c) \in R_+^{12}: N_h \leq \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} \\ (S_v, E_v, I_v) \in R_+^3: N_v \leq \frac{\Lambda_v}{\mu_v} \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

Is positively invariant and attracts all positive solutions of model (6)

Proof

Adding the first 12 equations as well as the last 3 equations of model (6) gives

$$\frac{dN_h}{dt} = \Lambda_h - \mu_h N_h - [\delta_3 E_{cd}^c + \delta_4 E_{cd}^d + \delta_1 I_d + \delta_2 I_c + (\delta_1 + \delta_2) I_{cd}] \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{dN_v}{dt} = \Lambda_v - \mu_v N_v \quad (10)$$

For the human population, we have

$$\frac{dN_h}{dt} \leq \Lambda_h - \mu_h N_h. \text{ So that } \frac{dN_h}{dt} + \mu_h N_h \leq \Lambda_h$$

Solving the differential inequality gives

$$N_h(t) \leq N_h(0)e^{-\mu_h t} + \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h}(1 - e^{-\mu_h t}) \quad (11)$$

Similarly, for the vector population, we have

$$N_v(t) \leq N_v(0)e^{-\mu_v t} + \frac{\Lambda_v}{\mu_v}(1 - e^{-\mu_v t}) \quad (12)$$

In particular,

$$N_h(t) \leq \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} \text{ if } N_h(0) \leq \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} \quad (13)$$

$$N_v(t) \leq \frac{\Lambda_v}{\mu_v} \text{ if } N_v(0) \leq \frac{\Lambda_v}{\mu_v} \quad (14)$$

For all $t > 0$. Hence, Ω_{cd} is a positively invariant set under the flow described by model (6). Furthermore, if $N_h(0) \geq \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h}$, then either the solution enters Ω_{cd} in finite time or $N_h(t)$ approaches to $\frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h}$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, no solution path leaves through any boundary of Ω_{cd} and the region Ω_{cd} attracts all solutions in R_+^{12} and R_+^3 . It is sufficient to study the dynamics of the flow generated by model (6) in Ω_{cd} .

2.3 Model Analysis

There are 3 models in this section; the two sub-models (dengue and COVID-19) and the coinfection model.

2.3.1 COVID-19 Only Model

We obtain the model

$$\frac{dS_w}{dt} = \Lambda_h - (\lambda_c + \mu_h)S_w$$

$$\frac{dE_c}{dt} = \lambda_c S_w - (\theta_c + \mu_h)E_c$$

$$\frac{dI_c}{dt} = \theta_c E_c - (\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)I_c \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = \varphi_2 I_c - (r_q + \mu_h)Q$$

$$\frac{dR_c}{dt} = r_c I_c + r_q Q - \mu_h R_c$$

Where

$$\lambda_c = \frac{\beta_c(1-kp)I_c}{N_h - Q} \tag{16}$$

The COVID-19 only model (15) has a DFE which is obtained by setting the right hand sides of equations in (15) to zero given by

$$\varepsilon_c = (S_w, E_c, I_c, Q, R_c) = \left(\frac{A_h}{\mu_h}, 0, 0, 0, 0\right) \tag{17}$$

The linear stability of the disease free equilibrium ε_c , can be established using the next generation operator method on model (15). Using the notations in Van den Driessche and Watmough (2002), it follows that the associated non-negative matrix F (of new infections) and the matrix V(of transition terms) gives the reproduction number of the COVID-19 only model given by

$$R_c = \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (1-kp)}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} \tag{18}$$

The reproduction number R_c of model (15) measures the average number of new COVID-19 cases generated by an infectious individual introduced into a population where personal protection strategy is implemented. We claim the following

Lemma 1: The DFE, ε_c of model (15) is locally asymptotically stable if $R_c < 1$ and unstable whenever $R_c > 1$. The implication of Lemma 1 is that the transmission of COVID-19 can be eliminated from the community when the basic reproduction number is less than unity ($R_c < 1$). This implies that $R_c < 1$ is sufficient but not necessary for the elimination of the disease. This means that even if $R_c > 1$, some number of persons will be infected even if there are no control measures implemented. Some of these persons will recover from the infection and since recovery confers permanent natural immunity, community wide natural herd immunity will be built and the disease will eventually die out.

Theorem 3: the unique endemic equilibrium of the COVID-19 only model (15) is globally asymptotically stable if $R_c < 1$.

Proof

Consider the lyapunov function given by

$$L = \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (1-kp)E}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} + \frac{\beta_c(\theta_c + \mu_h)(1-kp)I_c}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} \tag{19}$$

Differentiating with respect to t, gives

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (1-kp)}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} \frac{dE}{dt} + \frac{\beta_c(\theta_c + \mu_h)(1-kp)}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} \frac{dI_c}{dt}$$

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (1-kp)}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} [\lambda_c S_w - (\theta_c + \mu_h)E_c] + \frac{\beta_c(\theta_c + \mu_h)(1-kp)}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} [\theta_c E_c - (\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)I_c]$$

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (1-kp)}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} \lambda_c S_w - \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (\theta_c + \mu_h)(1-kp)E_c}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} + \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (\theta_c + \mu_h)(1-kp)E_c}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} - \beta_c (1 - kp)I_c$$

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (1-kp)}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)} \left[\frac{\beta_c (1-kp)I_c S_w}{N_h - Q} \right] - \beta_c (1 - kp)I_c$$

Since $S(t) \leq N - Q$ and $R_c = \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (1 - kp)}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + rc + \mu_h + \delta_2)}$, we have that

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \beta_c (1 - kp) \left[\frac{\beta_c \theta_c (1 - kp) I_c}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + rc + \mu_h + \delta_2)} - I_c \right]$$

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \beta_c (1 - kp) [R_c - 1] I_c$$

Hence, $\frac{dL}{dt} < 0$ if and only if $R_c < 1$ and $\frac{dL}{dt} = 0$ if and only if $I_c = 0$. Thus, L is a Lyapunov function for model (15). Thus, it follows by the LaSalle's principle that the DFE of model (15) is globally asymptotically stable whenever $R_c < 1$. The result above suggests the impossibility of backward bifurcation in model (15), since no endemic equilibrium exist.

2.3.2 Dengue Only Model

The dengue only model with host-vector parasite interaction is obtained below

$$\frac{dS_w}{dt} = \Lambda_h - (\lambda_d + \mu_h) S_w$$

$$\frac{dE_d}{dt} = \lambda_d S_w - (\theta_d + \mu_h) E_d$$

$$\frac{dI_d}{dt} = \theta_d E_d - (r_d + \mu_h + \delta_1) I_d$$

$$\frac{dR_d}{dt} = r_d I_d - \mu_h R_d$$

(20)

$$\frac{dS_v}{dt} = \Lambda_v - (\lambda_v + \mu_v) S_v$$

$$\frac{dE_v}{dt} = \lambda_v S_v - (\theta_v + \mu_v) E_v$$

$$\frac{dI_v}{dt} = \theta_v E_v - \mu_v I_v$$

Where $\lambda_d = \frac{\beta_d b I_v}{N_h}$ and $\lambda_v = \frac{\phi_7 \beta_v b I_d}{N_h}$

The dengue only model (15) has a DFE which is obtained by setting the right hand sides of equations in (15) to zero given by

$$\varepsilon_d = (S_w, E_d, I_d, R_d, S_v, E_v, I_v) = \left(\frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h}, 0, 0, 0, \frac{\Lambda_v}{\mu_v}, 0, 0 \right)$$

(21)

We also use the next-generation matrix to obtain the reproduction number as

$$R_d = \rho(FV^{-1}) = \sqrt{\frac{\beta_d \beta_v b^2 \theta_d \theta_v \Lambda_v \mu_h}{\Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (\theta_d + \mu_h)(r_d + \mu_h + \delta_1)(\theta_v + \mu_v)}}$$

(22)

Lemma 2: the disease free equilibrium, ε_d , of model (20) is locally asymptotically stable if $R_d < 1$ and unstable whenever $R_d > 1$.

The threshold quantity R_d of model (20) measures the average number of secondary cases that one infected individual can generate if introduced into a completely susceptible population. The epidemiological implication of Lemma 2 is that when $R_d < 1$, a small influx of infected mosquitoes into the community would not generate large outbreaks and the disease will die out in time (since the DFE is LAS).

2.3.3 Dengue – Corona virus coinfection Model

The feasible region for model (6) is given by

$$\Omega_{cd} = \Omega_c \times \Omega_d$$

(23)

Where Ω_c and Ω_d have been defined in the previous sections.

The DFE of model (6) is given by

$$\varepsilon_{cd} = (S, Ed, Ec, Id, Ic, Ecd, E_{cd}^c, E_{cd}^d, Icd, Q, Rd, Rc, Sv, Ev, Iv) = \left(\frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h}, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, \frac{\Lambda_v}{\mu_v}, 0, 0\right) \quad (24)$$

The associated reproduction number for the coinfection model (6) is given by

$$R_{cd} = \max\{R_c, R_d\} \quad (25)$$

We claim the following result

Lemma 3: the disease free equilibrium, ε_{cd} , of model (6) is locally asymptotically stable if $R_{cd} < 1$ and unstable whenever $R_{cd} > 1$.

The coinfection model might undergo the phenomenon of backward bifurcation. We have the result.

Theorem 4: if the bifurcation parameters $a > 0$ and $b > 0$, the coinfection model (6) will undergo the phenomenon of backward bifurcation at $R_{cd} = 1$.

Proof

We prove the existence of the phenomenon of backward bifurcation in model (6). Using the centre manifold theory, we change the variables for model (6). Thus we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx_1}{dt} &= \Lambda_h + \varphi_1 x_9 - (\lambda_d + \lambda_c + \mu_h)x_1 \\ \frac{dx_2}{dt} &= \lambda_d x_1 + \varphi_4 \lambda_d x_{12} - (\varphi_1 \lambda_c + \theta_d + \mu_h)x_2 \\ \frac{dx_3}{dt} &= \lambda_c x_1 + \varphi_3 \lambda_c x_{11} - (\varphi_2 \lambda_d + \theta_c + \mu_h)x_3 \\ \frac{dx_4}{dt} &= \varphi_1 \lambda_c x_2 + \varphi_2 \lambda_d x_3 - (\theta_{cd} + \mu_h)x_4 \\ \frac{dx_5^*}{dt} &= \varphi_5 \lambda_c x_7 - (\sigma_c + \mu_h + \delta_3)x_5^* \\ \frac{dx_6^*}{dt} &= \varphi_6 \lambda_d x_8 - (\sigma_d + \mu_h + \delta_4)x_6^* \\ \frac{dx_7}{dt} &= \theta_d x_2 - (\varphi_5 \lambda_c + r_d + \mu_h + \delta_1)x_7 \\ \frac{dx_8}{dt} &= \theta_c x_3 - (\varphi_6 \lambda_d + \varphi_2 + r_c + \mu_h + \delta_2)x_8 \\ \frac{dx_9}{dt} &= \theta_{cd} x_4 + \sigma_c x_5^* + \sigma_d x_6^* - (\varphi_1 + \mu_h + \delta_1 + \delta_2)x_9 \\ \frac{dx_{10}}{dt} &= \varphi_2 x_8 - (r_q + \mu_h)x_{10} \\ \frac{dx_{11}}{dt} &= r_d x_7 - (\varphi_3 \lambda_c + \mu_h)x_{11} \\ \frac{dx_{12}}{dt} &= r_c x_8 - (\varphi_4 \lambda_d + \mu_h)x_{12} \\ \frac{dx_{13}}{dt} &= \Lambda_v - (\lambda_v + \mu_v)x_{13} \\ \frac{dx_{14}}{dt} &= \lambda_v x_{13} - (\theta_v + \mu_v)x_{14} \\ \frac{dx_{15}}{dt} &= \theta_v x_{14} - \mu_v x_{15} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

With forces of infection given by

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_c &= \frac{\beta_c(1-kp)[x_8 + x_6 + x_9]}{N_h - Q} \\ \lambda_d &= \frac{\beta_d b x_{15}}{N_h} \\ \lambda_v &= \frac{\varphi_7 \beta_v b [x_7 + x_5 + I_{cd}]}{N_h} \end{aligned}$$

Next we consider the case when $R_d^2 = 1$. If β_d^* is the bifurcation parameter and $\beta_d = \beta_d^*$. solving for $\beta_d = \beta_d^*$ from $R_d^2 = 1$ gives

$$\beta_d = \beta_d^* = \frac{\Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (\theta_d + \mu_h)(r_d + \mu_h + \delta_1)(\theta_v + \mu_v)}{\beta_d \beta_v b^2 \theta_d \theta_v \Lambda_v \mu_h} \quad (27)$$

Now, we evaluate the Jacobian of the system (26) at the DFE ε_{cd} , denoted by $J(\varepsilon_{cd}^*)$ given by

$$J(\varepsilon_{cd}^*) = \begin{bmatrix} T_{11(8 \times 8)} & T_{12(8 \times 7)} \\ T_{21(7 \times 8)} & T_{22(7 \times 7)} \end{bmatrix}$$

The Jacobian $J(\varepsilon_{cd}^*)$ of (26) at $\beta_d = \beta_d^*$ written as $J \beta_d^*(\varepsilon_{cd}^*)$ has right eigenvector given by $W^* = (w_1^*, w_2^*, w_3^*, w_4^*, w_5^*, w_6^*, w_7^*, w_8^*, w_9^*, w_{10}^*, w_{11}^*, w_{12}^*, w_{13}^*, w_{14}^*, w_{15}^*)^T$ where

$$w_1^* = \frac{\Lambda_h \beta_d b w_{15} - \beta_c (1 - kp) \mu_h w_8}{\Lambda_h \mu_h}, w_2^* = \frac{\beta_d b w_{15}}{\theta_d + \mu_h}, w_3^* = \frac{\beta_c (1 - kp) \mu_h w_8}{\Lambda_h (\theta_d + \mu_h)}, w_4^* = w_5^* = w_6^* = w_9^* = 0,$$

$$w_7^* = \frac{\theta_d \beta_d b w_{15}}{(\theta_d + \mu_h)(rd + \mu_h + \delta_1)}, w_8^* = \frac{\theta_c \beta_d b w_{15}}{(\theta_d + \mu_h)(rc + \mu_h + \delta_1)}, w_{10}^* = \frac{\varphi_2 \theta_c \beta_d b w_{15}}{(\theta_d + \mu_h)(rc + \mu_h + \delta_1)(rq + \mu_h)}, w_{11}^* =$$

$$\frac{rd \theta_d \beta_d b w_{15}}{\mu_h (\theta_d + \mu_h)(rd + \mu_h + \delta_1)}, w_{12}^* = \frac{rc \theta_c \beta_d b w_{15}}{\mu_h (\theta_d + \mu_h)(rc + \mu_h + \delta_1)}, w_{13}^* = \frac{-\varphi_7 \beta_v b^2 \Lambda_v \mu_h \theta_d \beta_d w_{15}}{\Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (\theta_d + \mu_h)(rd + \mu_h + \delta_1)}, w_{14}^* = \frac{\mu_v w_{15}}{\theta_v}, w_{15}^* > w_{15}^*.$$

Similarly, $J \beta_d^*(\varepsilon_{cd}^*)$ has left eigenvector given by

$$V^* = (v_1^*, v_2^*, v_3^*, v_4^*, v_5^*, v_6^*, v_7^*, v_8^*, v_9^*, v_{10}^*, v_{11}^*, v_{12}^*, v_{13}^*, v_{14}^*, v_{15}^*) \text{ satisfying } V^* \cdot W^* = 1, \text{ with}$$

$$v_1^* = v_{10}^* = v_{11}^* = v_{12}^* = v_{13}^* = 0, v_2^* = \frac{\varphi_7 \beta_v b \Lambda_v \mu_h \theta_d v_{14}}{\Lambda_h \mu_v (\theta_d + \mu_h)(rd + \mu_h + \delta_1)}, v_3^* = \frac{\theta_c v_8}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)}, v_4^* =$$

$$\frac{\varphi_7 \beta_v b \Lambda_v \mu_h \theta_d v_{14} + \theta_c \beta_c (1 - kp) \mu_h v_3^*}{\Lambda_h \mu_v (\theta_c d + \mu_h)(\varphi_1 + \mu_h + \delta_1 + \delta_2)}, v_5^* = \frac{\varphi_7 \beta_v b \Lambda_v \mu_h v_{14} + \theta_c \Lambda_h \mu_v v_9}{\Lambda_h \mu_v (\theta_c d + \mu_h)(\varphi_1 + \mu_h + \delta_1 + \delta_2)}, v_6^* = \frac{\beta_c (1 - kp) \mu_h v_3^* + \theta_d \Lambda_h v_9}{\Lambda_h (\sigma_d + \mu_h + \delta_4)}, v_7^* =$$

$$\frac{\varphi_7 \beta_v b \Lambda_v \mu_h v_{14}}{\Lambda_h \mu_v (rd + \mu_h + \delta_1)}, v_8^* = \frac{\beta_c (1 - kp) \mu_h v_3^*}{\Lambda_h (rc + \mu_h + \delta_2)}, v_9^* = \frac{\varphi_7 \beta_v b \Lambda_v \mu_v \mu_h v_{14} + \beta_c (1 - kp) \mu_h v_3^*}{\Lambda_h \mu_v (\varphi_1 + \mu_h + \delta_1 + \delta_2)}, v_{14}^* > v_{14}^*, v_{15}^* =$$

$$\frac{\varphi_7 \beta_v b^2 \Lambda_v \mu_h \theta_d \beta_d v_{14}}{\Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (\theta_d + \mu_h)(rd + \mu_h + \delta_1)}.$$

After rigorous computation of the partial derivatives required for the computation of a and b, the bifurcation coefficients are given as

$$a = \frac{-2\beta_d b \mu_h V_2 W_{15}}{\Lambda_h} [w_2^* + w_3^* + w_7^* + w_8^* + w_{10}^* + w_{11}^* + w_{12}^*] - \frac{2\varphi_7 \beta_v b \Lambda_v \mu_h^2 w_{14} w_7^2}{\mu_v \Lambda_h^2} + \frac{2\varphi_7 \beta_v b v_{14} \mu_h w_7 w_{13}}{\Lambda_h} +$$

$$\frac{2\varphi_6 \beta_d b v_6 \mu_h w_{15}}{\Lambda_h} [w_3^* + w_8^*] + \frac{2\varphi_7 \beta_v b \Lambda_v \mu_h^2 w_{14} w_7}{\mu_v \Lambda_h^2} [w_2^* + w_3^* + w_7^* + w_8^* + w_{10}^* + w_{11}^* + w_{12}^*] \tag{28}$$

and

$$b = v_2 w_{15} b > 0. \tag{29}$$

obviously $b > 0$ for all biologically feasible parameter values. Thus, backward bifurcation occurs if and only if the following two parameters: the probability of effective transmission of dengue from infectious humans to susceptible aedes aegypti vectors (φ_7), the susceptibility of COVID-19 infected individuals to dengue infection (φ_6) are large enough such that $a > 0$. This implies that the effective reproduction number then becomes necessary and a sufficient tool for promoting control measures that will lead to disease eradication. Based on the result obtained above, we claim the following.

Theorem 5 (Non-existence of backward bifurcation): The model (6) or (26) does not undergo the phenomenon of backward bifurcation at $R_{cd} = 1$, whenever $\varphi_6 = \varphi_7 = 0$.

Proof

Consider the unique case of the model (6) with negligible parameters responsible for the existence of the backward bifurcation phenomenon (that is, $\varphi_6 = \varphi_7 = 0$). Then the backward bifurcation coefficient, a, reduces to

$$a = \frac{-2\beta_d b \mu_h V_2 W_{15}}{\Lambda_h} [w_2^* + w_3^* + w_7^* + w_8^* + w_{10}^* + w_{11}^* + w_{12}^*] \tag{30}$$

and $a < 0, b > 0$.

Hence, this study has confirmed that the presence of the following two parameters: (1) the probability of effective transmission of dengue from infectious humans to susceptible aedes aegypti vectors (φ_7) and (2) the

susceptibility of COVID-19 infected individuals to dengue infection (θ_6) activates backward bifurcation phenomenon in the epidemic dynamics of dengue coinfection with COVID-19.

Next, we establish the result for the impact of Dengue on COVID-19 and vice versa.

Lemma 4: An increase in the spread of dengue infection in the community will increase the pandemic of COVID-19.

Proof

To analyze the impact of Dengue on COVID-19, we begin by expressing the basic reproduction number R_c in terms of R_d . We now express the parameter μ_h in (22) in terms of R_d .

$$R_d = \sqrt{\frac{\beta_d \beta_v b^2 \theta_d \theta_v \Lambda_v \mu_h}{\Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (\theta_d + \mu_h)(rd + \mu_h + \delta_1)(\theta_v + \mu_v)}}$$

Solving for μ_h and simplifying gives

$$\mu_h = \frac{-\Lambda_h \mu_v^2 R_d^2 (\theta_v + \mu_v) + \sqrt{R_d^4 \Lambda_h^2 \mu_v^4 (\theta_d + \mu_h + \delta_1) + 4R_d^2 \Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (rd + \delta_1) Q - 4R_d^4 \Lambda_h^2 \mu_v^4 (\theta_v + \mu_v)^2 \theta_d (rd + \delta_1)}}{2R_d^2 \Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (\theta_v + \mu_v)} \tag{31}$$

Now let $h_1 = R_d^2 \Lambda_h^2 \mu_v^4 (\theta_d + \mu_h + \delta_1) + 4R_d^2 \Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (rd + \delta_1) Q - 4R_d^4 \Lambda_h^2 \mu_v^4 (\theta_v + \mu_v)^2 \theta_d (rd + \delta_1)$, $h_2 = \Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (\theta_v + \mu_v)$, $Q = \beta_d \beta_v b^2 \theta_d \theta_v \Lambda_v \mu_h$ So that

$$\mu_h = \frac{-\Lambda_h \mu_v^2 R_d^2 (\theta_v + \mu_v) + \sqrt{h_1}}{2R_d^2 \Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (\theta_v + \mu_v)} = \frac{-R_d^2 h_2 + \sqrt{h_1}}{2R_d^2 \Lambda_h \mu_v^2 (\theta_v + \mu_v)} \tag{32}$$

Substituting (32) into (18) gives

$$R_c = \frac{4R_d^4 h_2^2 \beta_c \theta_c (1 - kp)}{h_2^2 (2\theta_c - 1) R_d^4 [2(\varphi_1 + rc + \delta_2) - 1] + 2h_2 \sqrt{h_1} R_d^2 [(\theta_c + \varphi_1 + rc + \delta_2) - 2] + h_1}$$

The partial derivative of R_c with respect to R_d is given by

$$\frac{\partial R_c}{\partial R_d} = \frac{16R_d^3 h_2^2 h_1 \beta_c \theta_c (1 - kp)}{[h_2^2 (2\theta_c - 1) R_d^4 [2(\varphi_1 + rc + \delta_2) - 1] + 2h_2 \sqrt{h_1} R_d^2 [(\theta_c + \varphi_1 + rc + \delta_2) - 2] + h_1]^2} \tag{33}$$

Here we observe that $\frac{\partial R_c}{\partial R_d}$ is always positive. This means that the expansion of dengue infection increases the pandemic of COVID-19 since R_c is an increasing function of R_d .

Lemma 5: an increase in the spread of COVID-19 pandemic does not significantly affect the spread of dengue infection in the population.

Proof

We begin by expressing R_d in terms of R_c . We express the parameter μ_h in (18) in terms of R_c .

$$R_c = \frac{\beta_c \theta_c (1 - kp)}{(\theta_c + \mu_h)(\varphi_2 + rc + \mu_h + \delta_2)}$$

Solving for μ_h and simplifying gives

$$\mu_h = \frac{-R_c (\theta_c + k_3) + \sqrt{R_c^2 (\theta_c + k_3) + 4R_c \beta_c \theta_c (1 - kp) - 4R_c^2 \theta_c k_3}}{2R_c} \tag{34}$$

$$k_3 = (\varphi_2 + rc + \mu_h + \delta_2)$$

Now let

$$h_3 = R_c^2 (\theta_c + k_3) + 4R_c \beta_c \theta_c (1 - kp) - 4R_c^2 \theta_c k_3$$

so that

$$\mu_h = \frac{-R_c (\theta_c + k_3) + \sqrt{h_3}}{2R_c} = \frac{\sqrt{h_3} - R_c (\theta_c + k_3)}{2R_c} \tag{35}$$

Substituting (35) into (22) gives

$$R_d^2 = \frac{2\beta_d \beta_v b^2 \theta_d \theta_v \Lambda_v \mu_h [\sqrt{h_3} - R_c (\theta_c + k_3)]}{R_c [R_c (\theta_c + k_3) (\theta_c + k_3 - 2\theta_d) + 2(rd + \delta_1) (2\theta_d - \theta_c - k_3) + 2\sqrt{h_3} (\theta_d + rd + \delta_1 - \theta_c - k_3)] + h_3}$$

The partial derivative of R_d^2 with respect to R_c is given by

$$\frac{\partial R_d^2}{\partial R_c} = \frac{-2\beta_d \beta_v b^2 \theta_d \theta_v \Lambda_v \mu_h [2(\theta_c + k_3) \sqrt{h_3} (\theta_d + rd + \delta_1 - \theta_c - k_3) + h_3 k_3 + \sqrt{h_3} [(\theta_c + k_3) (\theta_c + k_3 - 2\theta_d) + 2(rd + \delta_1) (2\theta_d - \theta_c - k_3)]]}{[R_c [R_c (\theta_c + k_3) (\theta_c + k_3 - 2\theta_d) + 2(rd + \delta_1) (2\theta_d - \theta_c - k_3) + 2\sqrt{h_3} (\theta_d + rd + \delta_1 - \theta_c - k_3)] + h_3]^2}$$

We observe that R_c is a decreasing function of R_d . This means that increase in COVID-19 cases does not significantly affect the spread of Dengue infection in the population.

Conclusion

A new mathematical model for the co-dynamics of Dengue and COVID-19 coinfection has been developed. The model sub-divided the human population into 12 sub-populations and 3 vector sub-populations. Two sub-models and the coinfection model was generated. It was shown that the DFE of the sub-models were locally asymptotically stable if their reproduction numbers are less than unity. The covid-19 sub-model was shown to be globally asymptotically stable whenever the reproduction number is less than unity. The coinfection model exhibited the phenomenon of backward bifurcation at $R_{cd} = 1$ and it was shown that two parameters were responsible for the existence of backward bifurcation in the coinfection model (6) and the include; 1) the probability of effective transmission of dengue from infectious humans to susceptible aedes aegypti vectors (ϕ_7) and (2) the susceptibility of COVID-19 infected individuals to dengue infection (ϕ_6). It was also discovered that an increase in the spread of COVID-19 pandemic does not significantly affect the spread of dengue infection in the population and an increase in the spread of dengue infection in the population will increase the pandemic of COVID-19.

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